

MECHANICAL PERFORMANCE OF A POLYMER AND IRON TAILING COMPOSITE

Matheus Machado Lopes, University of Brasília, Brazil, machadomlopes@gmail.com
Michéle Dal Toé Casagrande, University of Brasília, Brazil, michele.casagrande@hotmail.com

ABSTRACT

Brazil was stage to environmental disasters involving tailing dams in the last decade. Forty million cubic meters of tailings were released into the environment with the rupture of Mariana's dam in 2015, reaching 663 kilometers of rivers and streams and 1,469 hectares of vegetation. In 2019, twelve million cubic meters with the rupture of Brumadinho's dam were released losing more than 230 human lives.

With technology advance, the demand for mineral materials just grows which leads to a corresponding production, and the greater the production, the greater the generation of tailings.

New measures to increase security of dams are being developed and alternate uses to these materials are being studied, this paper focus on the second case, studying a chemical stabilization of an iron tailing with polymer.

This study analyzed the addition of an acrylic-styrene copolymer to an iron tailing evaluating the best polymer dosage that leads to greater compressive strength and best compaction parameters. The samples were molded with the pure iron tailing optimum moisture content and the amount of polymer were added in mass to de amount of water, then the samples were left for 14 days to cure. After that, tests of Uniaxial Compression Strength (UCS) were made and the results showed that the 40% of polymer addition was the best dosage, with an increase higher than 1264% of strength compared to the pure tailing.

These initial results show that the addition of polymer to iron tailings is an efficient stabilization, opening possibilities for the study of application in geotechnical works such as landfills and paving.

KEYWORDS

Alternate Materials; New Geotechnical Materials; Stabilized Tailings.

INTRODUCTION

The mineral exploration activity in Brazil is one of the engines of the Brazilian economy. The sector generates more than 200,000 direct jobs, accounts for 4% of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and exports US\$ 50 billion per year, which corresponds to 25% of the country's export agenda (IBGM, 2019).

To meet the demand, it was necessary to develop new techniques for extracting ores, but even in the face of the growth of techniques, the lack of monitoring led to several accidents in tailings dams. In November 2015, with the failure of the Fundão dam, approximately 40 million cubic meters of mining tailings, composed mainly of silica and iron oxide, were released into the environment, reaching 663 kilometers of rivers and streams and 1,469 hectares of vegetation. Another accident occurred in January 2019, with the rupture of the dam at the Córrego do Feijão Mine, in Brumadinho in the state of Minas Gerais. The dam rupture released approximately 12 million cubic meters of iron ore tailings into the environment and the mud reached a distance greater than 85 kilometers from the point of rupture, reaching rivers and countless hectares of forests, causing the death of animals. and aquatic plants, in addition to irreversible damage to the environment. It should also be noted that the rupture led to more than 230 losses of human life.

In an attempt to reduce the possibility of similar tragedies in the future, several measures are being studied to deal with the source of this problem. One of the strategies used has been the attempt to reduce the liquefaction potential of tailings already disposed of in dams, taking measures to increase safety,

such as the use of soil improvement techniques to reduce the tailings void ratio (Kumar, 2001). Another strategy has focused on the use of tailings as a base or composite material for stabilizing slopes, building sub-base of pavements and embankments (Fahey et al. 2009; Consoli et al. 2008, 2009; Helinski et al. 2011; Carneiro, 2020; Silva, 2020).

The application of mining tailings in geotechnical works can be a way to make mining activity more sustainable, however, it is common that the geotechnical properties of a given material are not sufficient for its application in works, so it is necessary to use reinforcement for these materials.

Researches show that polymers are excellent soil stabilizers and can be applied as sealants on unpaved roads, to protect against erosion and to improve slope stability, as they promote grain agglutination and improve matrix stability.

According to Bachini et al. (2016), polymers have superior durability to Portland cement, have resistance to acid attack and influence the mechanical properties and workability of the mixtures.

Experimental results presented by Silva (2020) and Carneiro (2020), involving mechanical and leaching analysis, indicate that with an adequate technological control of execution, the polymer proposed here brings positive results to the hydraulic and mechanical behavior of granular materials and does not cause damage environmental.

With that in mind, this paper aims to investigate the resistance gain of an iron tailing stabilized with different polymer dosages of 10%, 20%, 30%, 40%, 50% and 60% after 14 days of cured samples and evaluate which dosage works better with this iron tailing.

MATERIALS

Iron Tailing

The iron tailing come from the Maravilhas II dam mine located at Mina do Pico in the city of Itabirito, Minas Gerais. Maravilhas II is one of the 13 dams that make up the Vargem Grande Complex, four of which are tailings dams, and also comprises six mines, eight plants and three cargo terminals. This complex is operated by Vale.

It is one of the main dams in the Complex, which currently operates only 1 million tons per year, although its total capacity is 42.9 million tons per year. The Maravilhas II Dam is of the downstream type, implemented in 1994, has a volume of 94 million cubic meters, has a height of 97.9 meters and currently has 109 monitoring instruments (CMBH, 2019).

The tailing is composed mostly by iron (hematite) and silicon (quartz), in a proportion of 55% and 40% respectively. The missing 5% is composed by aluminium and manganese.

Polymer

The polymer TERRAFIX 11 (CAS: 25035-69-2) was used in this research, consisting of an acrylic-styrene copolymer, obtained at random. Being an aqueous emulsion of anionic character. Produced and distributed by the company Waterflows. It has a pH of 8.0–9.0, density of 0.98–1.04 grams per cubic centimeter. In addition, it is completely soluble in water. According to the manufacturer, the product can be used as a sealant (dust reducer) and as a soil stabilizer. Due to commercial and industrial secrecy issues, the quali-quantitative composition was not provided by the manufacturer.

METHODS

Granulometry

The granulometry tests were made according to ABNT NBR 7181 (ABNT, 2016), in triplicate, with and without defoculant. To execute this test is necessary to obtain the real density of the iron tailing grains, and this data was obtained using a pentapycnometer.

Compaction Test

The compaction test was carried out for the pure iron tailing according to the DNER-ME 228/94 standard (DNER, 1994) with normal energy of compaction.

Uniaxial Compression Strength

Uniaxial compression strength tests were performed according to the methods established by NBR 12770 (ABNT, 2022). Using the compaction curve for the tailing, the moisture content was fixated in 19%, corresponding to the maximum specific dry weight and samples of composite tailing + polymer were made in the percentages of 10, 20, 30, 40, 50 and 60 of polymer solubilized in water. It means that the composite Tailing + 10% of Polymer for example, were made with 19%, in weight, of solution water + polymer, which means it has 1.9% of polymer, in weight; the composite Tailing + 20% of Polymer has 3.8%, the Tailing + 30% of Polymer has 5.7% and so on. The samples were left for cure for 14 days, only after they were tested.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Based on the granulometric analysis and Figure 1 below is able to notice that the iron tailing is composed for the most part by a fraction similar to sand, 92.7%, followed by a little fraction similar to silt, 5.8% and a smaller fraction similar to clay, 1.5%. The real density of the iron tailing grains, obtained in the pentapycnometer, was 3.23 g/cm³.

Figure 1: Iron Tailing Granulometry

Despite the fact that the figure shows a granular behavior like sand, when in contact with water this material presents an extremely similar behavior to that of a clay soil using a visual tactile analysis. It reminds that the material in study is an iron tailing not a soil, from a granulometric point of view, it is acceptable to establish a parallel to the size of the particles, however, caution is necessary when extrapolating the issues related to the behavior that can be induced by the granulometric classification. The Figure 2 shows the results for the compaction test. The maximum specific dry weight obtained was 23.4 kN/m³ with an optimum moisture content of 19% approximately. Analysing this curve is possible to notice that the shape of the curve is very similar to a plastic clay soil curve, which corroborates the visual tactile analysis and differs from the granulometry. An explanation to this divergence is that the iron tailing didn't suffer weathering as the plastic clay soil suffered, the iron tailing is a by-product of the beneficiation process of the tailing which passes through significant physical and chemical processes that can alter the behavior of the material.

Figure 2: Tailing Compaction Curve

Figure 3 shows the Void Ratio corresponding to the compaction curve, the maximum specific dry weight has the minimum void ratio which is 0.13.

Figure 3: Void Ratio

Figure 4 below shows the results for de UCS tests performed. From the graphic is possible to notice that the addition of polymer resulted in a resistance growth up to 40% Polymer, after that the resistance decreases with the addition of polymer.

In addition, is notable that the polymer gives a large improvement to the iron tailing peak resistance, but it doesn't present a nice post-peak resistance showing that it has a fragile behavior.

UCS tests in pure iron tailing were performed but the stress presented by the samples were smaller than the load cell available in the laboratory could measure, which means is even smaller than the Tailing + 10% of Polymer composite.

Figure 4: Stress X Strain of Multiple Polymer Percentages

The Table 1 shows the Maximum Stress to each composite tested and the percentage of Stress gain compared to the first composite. As it shows, the Tailing + 40% of Polymer composite presented the higher Maximum Stress, with an 1264% of growth compared to the Tailing + 10% of Polymer.

Table 1: Maximum Stress

Composite	Maximum Stress (kPa)	% of Growth (Compared to the first composite)
Tailing + 10% of Polymer	263	---
Tailing + 20% of Polymer	753	286
Tailing + 30% of Polymer	2114	804
Tailing + 40% of Polymer	3324	1264
Tailing + 50% of Polymer	2574	979
Tailing + 60% of Polymer	2175	827

Figure 5 below shows the tested samples and their planes of rupture. It is visible that the (a) and (b) samples present total rupture, sample (c) presents an approximately 90 degrees angle of rupture, (d), (e) and (f) presented an approximately 45 degrees angle of rupture. Besides the samples don't present high post-peak resistance, it was not possible to separate the sides of the samples (c), (d), (e) and (f) with bare hands, showing a high cohesive structure.

Figure 5: Tested Samples and Their Plane of Rupture

CONCLUSION

This paper shows preliminary results of a bigger research about this specific iron tailing and the application of polymer in it. The main goal of it was to study the best polymer dosage to use with this iron tailing i.e., the composite that presented the higher compression resistance.

Analysing the results is possible to notice that the pure iron tailing doesn't have good mechanical properties by itself based on compression resistance analysis, due to the fact that the load cell wasn't even capable of detecting its resistance.

The addition of polymer in the iron tailing was very positive towards the compression resistance of the material, even the slightest addition of polymer (10%) resulted in a significant gain of compression resistance to the iron tailing. The results show that the addition of 40% of polymer to the iron tailing was the best dosage, representing an enormous gain of resistance of 1264%, but the 30% of polymer addition was a good dosage as well, considering that it has a gain of resistance of 804% with the advantage that it was a lower amount of polymer. This can be considered a good dosage because considering an application in field it can represent savings in the total cost of a geotechnical work.

In general, the use of polymer with tailings in geotechnical work has shown a great way of destination to those tailings, giving them enough mechanical properties to being used as geotechnical materials. It can be considered a sustainable alternative to those tailings, because the polymer shows no significant impact to the environment as shown by Silva (2020), Cordeiro (2020) and Alelvan (2022).

This paper gives a north to the main research with this iron tailing reinforced with a polymer, bounding better ways of using the composite like the best dosages, the best moistures to use with, unconfined mechanical behavior of the composite as peak, post-peak as planes of rupture. Future perspectives are analysing shear strength of the composites, discovering how the polymer acts in the voids of the iron tailing using tomography images and trying to predict a behavior of resistance based on dosage, compaction, moisture and void ratio.

CITATIONS

ABNT (1984). *Soil - Grain size analysis: NBR 7181*. 13p.

ABNT (2022). *Soil - Determination of the unconfined compressive strength of cohesive soil*. 6p.

Alelvan, G. M. (2022). *Análise Mecânica e Microestrutural de Rejeito de Minério de Ouro Estabilizado com Solução Polimérica*. Doctoral Thesis, Publication G.DM – 343/2022 Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering, University of Brasília, Brasília, DF, 171p.

Bachini, M.S., Ismail, A., Naserlavi, S.S. & Firoozi, A.A. (2016) *Performance Evaluation of Road Base Stabilized with Styrene-Butadiene Copolymer Latex and Portland Cement*. Elsevier, Construction and Building Materials, 16p.

Carneiro, A. A. (2020). *Comportamento mecânico de um rejeito de minério de ferro estabilizado com polímero e do compósito rejeito-polímero reforçado com fibras de Polipropileno*. Doctoral Thesis, Publication G.DM- 162/20 Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering, University of Brasília, Brasília, DF, 146p.

CMBH (2019, June 18). *Maravilhas II só voltará a operar após laudo previsto para setembro*. <https://www.cmbh.mg.gov.br/comunicação/notícias/2019/06/maravilhas-ii-só-voltará-operar-após-laudo-previsto-para-setembro>.

Consoli, N.C., Thomé, A., Donato, M., Graham, J. (2008). *Loading tests on compacted soil, bottom-ash and lime layers*. Proceedings of the Institution of Civil Engineers - Geotechnical Engineering, 161(GE1): 29–38. doi:10.1680/geng.2008.161.1.29.

Consoli, N.C., Dalla Rosa, F., Fonini, A. (2009). *Plate load tests on cemented soil layers overlaying weaker soil*. Journal of Geotechnical and Geoenvironmental Engineering, 135(12): 1846–1856. doi:10.1061/(ASCE)GT.1943-5606.0000158.

DNER (1994). *DNER-ME 228/94 “Solos – compactação em equipamento miniatura”*. 14p.

Fahey, M., Helisnki, M., Fourie, A. (2009). *Some aspects of the mechanics of arching in backfilled stopes*. Canadian Geotechnical Journal, 46(11): 1322–1336. doi:10.1139/T09-063.

Helisnki, M., Fahey, M., Fourie, A. (2011). *Behavior of cemented paste backfill in two mine stopes: measurement and modeling*. Journal of Geotechnical and Geoenvironmental Engineering, 137(2): 171–182. doi:10.1061/(ASCE)GT.1943-5606.0000418.

IBGM (2019, August 15) *A Mineração de Ouro no Brasil*. Instituto Brasileiro de Gemas & Metais Preciosos. <https://ibgm.com.br/a-mineracao-de-ouro-no-brasil/>.

Silva, N.A.B.S. (2020). *Desempenho de um compósito solo-polímero para aplicabilidade em obras geotécnicas e de pavimentação*. Master's Dissertation, Publication G.DM-339/20 Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering, University of Brasília, Brasília, DF, 111p.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The work presented in this paper was partially supported by CNPq.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

All necessary data is presented in this paper.